

Resolving system failures in bin-picking tasks through human-robot collaboration

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Abstract—The automation of bin-picking tasks has been a research topic for almost two decades. However, general-purpose equipment still does not show adequate success rate to find application in most industrial tasks. In this extended abstract, starting from a general-purpose industrial bin-picking device composed of a 3D-structured light vision system and a collaborative robot arm, we show how its performance can be improved and its possible applications enhanced through human-robot collaboration.

Index Terms—Bin-picking, Collaborative robotics, Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), Industry 4.0/5.0

I. INTRODUCTION

Bin-picking consists in grasping objects randomly placed in a bin for subsequent positioning in a different place and pose. Its automation through a robot arm and a 3D vision sensor has been actively studied over the past two decades [1], [2]. Full automation of bin-picking applications is rather challenging because it involves 3D data acquisition and object recognition through sophisticated computer vision algorithms, pose estimation, optimal end-effector design and correct grasp planning of overlapping complex objects. As a consequence, applications of robotic bin-picking are often difficult to implement, failure rates in robotic bin picking are still high for practical industrial applications and handling mixed bins that contain multiple different types of parts with complex or unknown geometry remains an open and challenging task.

Because humans and robots share complementary strengths in performing tasks, a collaborative bin-picking cell where robots and humans work in close proximity can enhance bin-picking success rates, increase system flexibility and productivity while improving the operators' working conditions. Despite current interest and advances in collaborative robotics, few previous studies have investigated the collaboration between robots and human operators in bin-picking tasks [3]–[7]. However, in these works, human-robot collaboration was limited and not exploited to its full potential. For this reason, we introduced a novel framework for bin-picking [9], where an human operator working alongside the robot can help

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Fig. 1. Human-robot collaboration when resolving bin-picking failures

quickly and easily solve faults when they occur using collaborative functions such as manual hand guidance or collision detection.

II. COLLABORATIVE HUMAN-ROBOT BIN-PICKING

In robotic bin-picking several types of failures can occur, which can be classified as follows: object recognition failures, pose estimation failures, grasping failures and failures because of constraints on robot motion. These failures typically require the line to be paused, human intervention to enter the workcell (thus, entering safety fences), clear the fault (for example, pick the entangled objects and either separate or discard them), and restart the line. Other research groups focused on decreasing bin-picking failure rates by developing more complex computer vision algorithms or more efficient grippers. However, many commercial bin-picking solutions do not allow to access directly to the acquired 3D nor to customize the computer vision algorithms used for object recognition. For this reason, we focused on improving the fault tolerance of an already existing workcell through human-robot collaboration, combining the best features of both operators and robots. Figure 1 shows human-robot collaboration when resolving different types of bin-picking failures.

III. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS

The proposed framework was tested in some simple yet significant tests. The robotic workcell exploited during the tests is composed of a 6 axis collaborative robot arm and a 3D structured light sensor. The objects picked from the bin

Fig. 2. Example of a failure because of constraints in robot motion: (a) results of object recognition (the highlighted nut is recognized but cannot be picked), (b) constraints in robot motion (bin faces), and (c) resolution of the fault by manual pick of the part.

Fig. 3. Example of a perception failure: (a) results of object recognition and magnification of the 3D point map acquired (it has too few points due to reflectance properties of the surface), (b) Fault resolution by manual hand guidance to the pick pose.

during the experimental tests are M30 hexagon nuts: because of their reflectance properties, they can be difficult to detect.

To ensure safety, the system performs collision avoidance, both between the robot end effector and the faces of the bin and between the robot end effector and human operator. The presence of human operators inside the workcell is detected using the same vision sensor used for 3D data acquisition. Taking into account the limitation of the hardware and software used, we assumed that the operator wears a special bracelet with geometric shapes that are easy to detect by the vision sensor. We then implemented a computer vision algorithm that detects and tracks the human operator. During operations, the robot's speed is adjusted according to its relative distance from the operator. Moreover, in the robot used during the experimental tests, manual hand guidance is an option that we, unfortunately, did not purchase. For this reason, we implemented an admittance controller [9] exploiting data from the force sensor mounted on the robot's wrist.

Figure 2 and 3 represents and example of two different types of bin-picking failures that may occur and their solving through human-robot collaboration. When bin-picking fails because of constraints in robot motion (Figure 2), the cobot recognizes that the part cannot be picked and seeks external help from the operator by turning the gripper LED strip light red. The human operator then manually perform bin-picking and subsequent placement of the part. On the other hand, when perception failures (Figure 3) occur, the human operator can manually move the robot above the grasping pose by pushing it directly, exploiting manual hand guidance. Once the robot has been moved to the pick position, the operator notifies the cobot by simply touching it, exploiting collaborative features (i.e., the robot ability to detect contacts). The robot then proceeds to approach and pick the part. The bin-picking execution task is restored and the fault is quickly and easily cleared.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this extended abstract, we showed how human-robot collaboration in bin-picking tasks can improve success rates, increase system flexibility and productivity, and reduce downtimes. The proposed strategy was tested in some simple tests, proving that collaborative functions can be useful in overcoming typical bin-picking failures.

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